

PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF WASTE COOKING OIL & SOYABEAN OIL BLENDS WITH DIESEL

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, oil prices have been rising rapidly again and there is a major concern for the long term availability of fossil fuels. This and the growing concern for our environment have created a much larger market for renewable resources. The idea of using vegetable oils instead of fossil diesel fuels has resurfaced as a way to minimize the net carbon footprint left by emissions from compression ignition (CI) engines. Straight vegetable oils (SVOs) have their fair share of problems in unmodified CI engines. These problems include: cold-weather starting; plugging and gumming of filters lines, and injectors; engine knocking; coking of injectors on piston and head of engine; carbon deposits on piston and head of engine; excessive engine wear; and deterioration of engine lubricating oil. Vegetable oils decrease power output and thermal efficiency while leaving carbon deposits inside the cylinder.

To avoid some of these problems, vegetable oils have been converted via a chemical process (transesterification) to result in a fuel more like fossil diesel. The resulting fuel is biodiesel, a biodegradable and nontoxic renewable fuel. Furthermore, biodiesels have reduced molecular weights (in relation to triglycerides), reduced viscosity, and improved volatility when compared to ordinary vegetable oils. Most CI engines can run on biodiesels without modifications; however to optimize combustion the injection timing should be adjusted.

Biodiesel is a fuel made mostly from crops with seeds that contain oil. In tropical regions, palm and jatropha are promising oilseed crops. Biodiesel can also be made from used cooking oil and animal fats. Biodiesel typically has a higher cetane rating than petroleum diesel. The cetane rating is a measure of diesel's combustion quality – similar to an octane rating for gasoline.

SPECIFICATION OF BIODIESEL

Standards are of vital importance for the producers, suppliers and users of biofuels. Authorities need approval standards for the evaluation of safety, risks and environmental protection. Standards are necessary for the approval and warrantee commitment for vehicles operated with bio-fuels and are therefore, a pre-requisite for the market introduction and commercialization of bio-fuels. Creation of standards shall help expand the market for renewable sources of energy in India. Conventionally standards and codes for products have been developed, largely by examining the existing standards and codes in different countries and then writing standards for own country. A worldwide survey of bio-diesel specification was done and an attempt was made to understand the rationale behind them before proposing a norm for India. The key components, which determine the quality of biodiesel, are monoalkylesters, dialkyl esters, residual vegetable oil, free glycerin, reactant alcohol, free fatty acids and the residual catalyst. In December 2001, American Society of Testing and Materials (ASTM) issued a specification (D6751) for biodiesel (B100) which is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. ASTM Specification (D6751) for biodiesel (B100)

Property	ASTM Method	Limits	Units
Flash Point	D93	130 min	Degrees C
Water & Sediment	D2709	0.050 max.	% Volume
Kinematic Viscosity	D445	1.9-6.0	mm ² /sec
Copper Strip Corrosion	D130	No.3 max.	-
Cetane	D613	47 min.	-
Cloud Point	D2500	Report	Degrees C
Carbon Residue (100% Sample)	D4530	0.050 max.	% mass
Acid Number	D664	0.80 max.	Mg KOH/gm
Free Glycerin	D6584	0.020 max	% mass
Total Glycerin	D6584	0.240 max.	% mass

Table no.2. Specification of Soyabean Oil Biodiesel

	Method	Unit	Spec	Typical
Acid Value ¹	EN14104	mg KOH/g	0.5 max	0.30
Iodine Value ¹	EN14111	% (m/m)	120 max	52
Water Content (Sediment + water) ¹	ENISO12937	mg/kg	1000 max	600
Ester Content ¹	EN14103	% (m/m)	98.5	98.5
Cold Filter Plugging Pt C ²	EN 116	°C	15 max	13
Pour point C	EN ISO 3016	°C	20 max	18+
Flash Point ²	ENISO3679	°C	120 min	160
Cetane Number ²	ENISO5165	-	51.0 min	58.5
Methanol Content ¹	EN14110	% (m/m)	0.2 max	0.2
Density at 15°C ²	ENISO3674	kg/cm ³	0.850-0.900	0.899
Viscosity at 40°C ²	ENISO3104	mm ² /s	3.50- 5.00	4.5
Sulphur Content ²	ENISO20846 ENISO20884	mg/kg	10 max	<0.015
Carbon Residue (on 10% distillation residue) ²	ENISO10370	% (m/m)	0.3 max	0.01
Sulphated Ash Content ²	ISO3987	% (m/m)	0.02 max	0.001
Total Contamination ²	EN12662	mg/kg	24 max	0.1
Copper Strip Corrosion (3h at 50°C) ²	ENISO2160	Rating	Class 1	Class 1
Oxidation Stability 110°C ²	EN14112	Hours	6.0 min	8.0
Linolenic Acid Methyl Ester Polyunsaturated (>=4 double bonds) Methyl Esters	EN14103	% (m/m)	12.0 max	9.3
Monoglyceride Content ²	EN14105	% (m/m)	1 max	0.2
Diglyglyceride Content ²	EN14105	% (m/m)	0.8 max	0.136
Triglyceride Content ²	EN14105	% (m/m)	0.2 max	0.025
Free Glycerol ¹	EN14105	% (m/m)	0.2 max	<0.001
Total Glycerol ²	EN14105	% (m/m)	0.10 max	0.011
Group 1 Metals (Na+K) ²	EN14108 EN14109	mg/kg	0.25 max	0.039
Group 2 Metals (Ca+Mg) ²	EN14108 EN14109	mg/kg	5.0 max	<5
Phosphorus Content ²	EN14538 EN14107	mg/kg	5.0 max	<5
			10.0 max	0.01

SINGLE CYLINDER VARIABLE COMPRESSION CI

The VCR engine provides excellent fuel flexibility, since the compression ratio can be varied and adjusted to suit the properties of the fuel, and therefore the engine will always run at the compression ratio best suited to the fuel being used. Compression ratio is an important parameter in any engine, which decides performance of the engine. With increase in compression ratio in diesel engine, its break power increases. This also leads to increase in

mechanical efficiency. Further relative decrease in clearance volume leads to increase in volumetric efficiency. At the same time, it leads to increase in specific fuel consumption (SFC). This will affect the overall performance of the engine. It becomes necessary to conduct the trial on engine to find out the overall performance of the engine at various compression ratios. In this trial, we can compare the performance of the engine at various loads by various parameters like brake thermal efficiency, specific fuel consumption, volumetric efficiency etc.

Fig.No.01.Experimental set up

Experimental set up consist of 4 stroke, water cooled diesel engine. Eddy current dynamometer is coupled with engine for loading arrangement. Above Fig 5.1.1 shows the experimental set up.

Fig.No.2.Compression ratio adjustment

Following procedure should be followed to change the compression ratio,

- Slightly loosen 6 Allen bolts provided for clamping the tilting block.
- Loosen the lock nut on the adjuster and rotate the adjuster so that the compression ratio is set to “maximum”. Refer the marking on the CR indicator.
- Lock the adjuster by the lock nut.
- Tighten all the 6 Allen bolts gently.
- You may measure and note the center distance between two pivot pins of the CR indicator. After changing the compression ratio the difference (Δ) can be used to know new CR.

From Fig 2. We get idea about changing the compression ratio.

Fig.3.VCR Engine Instrumentation Details

Figure 3. shows the engine cooling arrangement and the inlet air supply system to the engine.

Fig.4. VCR Engine Calorimeter and Thermocouple Details

Figure .4 shows the position of various temperature sensors and calorimeter details like calorimeter support structure, pump bracket etc. The meaning of various temperature indicators is mentioned in performance table.

Fig.5.VCR Engine Dynamometer and Load Indicator Details

Figure 5. Indicates the control panel and the dynamometer arrangement. The control panel consist of load indicator, fuel cock, fuel measuring pipe, temperature digital indicator.

Dynamometer water inlet and the outlet is shown in the right side diagram.

Table 3. Engine Specifications

Manufacturer	M/s Kirloskar Oil Engines Ltd.
Model	TV 1
Cycle	4 STROKES
Rated Power	3.5 kW @ 1500 RPM
Type of Combustion System	Direct Injection
No. of Cylinders	1 Cylinder
Bore/Stroke	87.5 /110 mm
Compression Ratio	17.5 : 1 Modified to VCR 12 to18 : 1

PERFORMANCE TESTING

During performance testing of waste cooking oil and soyabean oil blends with pure diesel on 4 stroke, water cooled CI engine following observations were recorded, these are given in following table.

Table 4.Performance Characteristics

Fuel	Blend	Jacket water (LPH)	Cal. Water (LPH)	Load (kg)	Engine water in temp. T ₁ (°C)	Engine water out T ₂ (°C)	Cal. water in temp T ₃ (°C)	Cal. water out Temp T ₄ (°C)	Ex. gas cal. inlet temp. T ₅ (°C)	Ex. gas cal. outlet temp. T ₆ (°C)	Man o. Deflection	Time for 10CC fuel consumption (sec)
Pure Diesel		90	94	3	27	45	27	37	192	150	45	60
		110	130	6	27	48	27	37	210	156	45	48
		110	130	9	27	53	27	37	249	180	46	28
Wco + Diesel	B10	110	130	3	27	43	27	35	195	153	43	51
		110	130	6	27	43	27	35	213	165	43	48
		110	130	9	27	46	27	37	249	183	47	36
	B20	110	130	3	27	40	27	34	174	135	45	52
		110	130	6	27	46	27	36	207	159	45	47
		110	130	9	27	51	27	41	237	177	45	37
	B25	60	100	3	27	48	27	34	189	144	45	65
		60	100	6	27	52	27	34	219	165	45	51
		60	100	9	27	54	27	35	249	180	47	41
Soya + Diesel	B10	150	175	3	27	45	27	32	176	122	83	54
		150	175	6	27	42	27	32	182	118	82	41
		150	175	9	27	47	27	33.3	231	150	80	35
	B20	150	175	3	27	40	27	31	165	116	84	58
		150	175	6	27	43	27	32	196	131	82	43
		150	175	9	27	46	27	32	233.3	152	80	34
	B25	150	175	3	27	39	27	32	175	122	92	54
		150	175	6	27	44	27	32	195	132	86	45
		150	175	9	27	45	27	33.3	231	151	84	36

RESULTS

Table 4. PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF WASTE COOKING OIL & SOYABEAN OIL BLENDS WITH DIESEL

During trial on four strokes, water cooled CI engine using waste cooking oil and soyabean oil blends with diesel with varying percentage and following test conditions are found as follows:

Speed = 1490 Rpm

Blends = B10, B20, B25 for both the oils

Load used = 3, 6, 9 kg

Fuel	Blends	Loads (kg)	BP (KW)	BMEP (bar)	BSFC (Kg/Kwh)	$\eta_{bth}(\%)$	Air flow (kg/h)	Fuel flow (kg/h)	$\eta_{vol}(\%)$
Pure diesel		3	0.85	1.03	0.59	14.62	21.78	0.50	63.15
		6	1.70	2.07	0.37	23.40	21.78	0.62	63.15
		9	2.55	3.10	0.42	20.47	22.02	1.07	63.85
Wco + Diesel	B10	3	0.85	1.03	0.69	12.43	21.29	0.59	61.73
		6	1.70	2.07	0.37	23.40	21.29	0.62	61.73
		9	2.55	3.10	0.33.33	26.32	22.26	0.83	64.54
	B20	3	0.85	1.03	0.68	12.67	21.78	0.57	63.15
		6	1.70	2.07	0.37	22.91	21.78	0.64	63.15
		9	2.55	3.10	0.32	27.05	21.78	0.81	63.15
	B25	3	0.85	1.03	0.54	15.84	21.78	0.46	63.15
		6	1.70	2.07	0.34	24.86	21.78	0.59	63.15
		9	2.55	3.10	0.29	29.98	22.26	0.73	64.54
Soya + Diesel	B10	3	0.85	1.03	0.65	13.16	29.57	0.55	85.77
		6	1.70	2.07	0.43	19.99	29.40	0.73	85.25
		9	2.55	3.10	0.33.33	25.59	29.04	0.85	84.20
	B20	3	0.86	1.03	0.60	14.23	29.75	0.52	85.71
		6	1.71	2.07	0.41	21.10	29.40	0.69	84.68
		9	2.55	3.10	0.34	24.86	29.04	0.88	84.20
	B25	3	0.85	1.03	0.65	13.16	31.14	0.55	90.30
		6	1.70	2.07	0.39	21.94	30.10	0.66.67	87.30
		9	2.55	3.10	0.33.33	26.32	29.75	0.83	86.28

RESULT & DISCUSSION

EFFECT ON BRAKE POWER OF THE ENGINE:

An experimental result shows that the break power developed by the engine at all the loads for different blends of the fuel is same. Since the operating speed of the engine is 1490 rpm which is constant. Fig 6.represents the effect of break power Vs the load on the engine.

Fig.6. Brake Power Vs Load for Diesel, B10, B20, B25 for Both Oils

EFFECT ON BRAKE SPECIFIC FUEL CONSUMPTION OF THE ENGINE:

From the experimental results we can say that B10 & B20 of both the oils shows the more or less same results at full load which are less than pure diesel. At 33.33% load diesel & SOYA B20 have same values of bsfc, while at 66.67% load WCO B10 & B20 have same value of bsfc. In comparison with SOYA B25, WCO B25 requires less fuel at all the loads while WCO B10 & B20 requires same fuel but more than B25. At 33.33% load SOYA B10 & B25 shows same bsfc while at 66.67% load B10 requires slightly high fuel than B20 & B25. At full load all blends of SOYABEAN requires same fuel supply. WCO B25 has good performance than SOYA B25 for brake specific fuel consumption.

Fig 7. Brake Specific Fuel Consumption Vs Load for B10

Fig 8- Brake Specific Fuel Consumption Vs Load for B20

Fig 9.Brake Specific Fuel Consumption Vs Load for B25

Fig 10. Brake Specific Fuel Consumption Vs Load for B25

Fig 11. Brake Specific Fuel Consumption Vs Load for all WCO

Fig12. Brake Specific Fuel Consumption Vs Load for Diesel & WCO B25

Fig 13. Brake Specific Fuel Consumption Vs Load for Diesel, WCO B25 & Soya B25

EFFECT ON BRAKE THERMAL EFFICIENCY OF THE ENGINE:

At the load of 33.33% SOYA B10 & B25 shows the lower efficiencies than corresponding blends of WCO while B20 blend has higher efficiency than its corresponding blend. WCO B10 & B20 has almost similar efficiencies but lower than B25. On the other hand SOYA B10 & B25 shows the lower efficiencies than B20.

All the blends of SOYA have poor efficiencies than WCO at the load of 66.67%. WCO B10 & B20 has more or less similar efficiencies & WCO B25 has slightly higher than both the blends. SOYA B10, B20, B25 has slightly higher efficiencies than each other respectively.

WCO B20 & B25 shows high brake thermal efficiencies than corresponding blends of SOYA. WCO B10 & B20 has more or less similar values which are less than WCO B25. SOYA blends has same values with slight change.

WCO B25 has more brake thermal efficiency than SOYA B25 at every operating load on the engine.

Fig 14. Brake Thermal Efficiency Vs Load for Diesel, WCO B10, SOYA B10

Fig 15. Brake Thermal Efficiency Vs Load for Diesel, WCO B20 & SOYA B20

Fig 16. Brake Thermal Efficiency Vs Load for WCO B20 & DIESEL

Fig 17. Brake Thermal Efficiency Vs Load for Diesel, SOYA B10, SOYA B20, SOYA B25

Fig 18. Brake Thermal Efficiency Vs Load for Diesel, WCO B10, WCO B20 & WCO B25

Fig 19. Brake Thermal Efficiency Vs Load for WCO B25 & DIESEL

Fig 20. Brake Thermal Efficiency Vs Load for WCO B20 & DIESEL

EFFECT ON VOLUMETRIC EFFICIENCY OF THE ENGINE:

All WCO blends have same volumetric efficiencies than that off diesel with slight changes. SOYA blends has more volumetric efficiency than WCO blends.

SOYA B25 shows higher volumetric efficiency than B10 & B20 which is more than pure diesel. WCO B10 has poor volumetric efficiency than diesel. On the other hand WCO B20 & B25 has same efficiency like diesel up to the load of 66.67% then after diesel has volumetric efficiency in between B20 & B25. WCO B20 shows almost same value of volumetric efficiency at all operating loads.

Fig 21. Volumetric Efficiency Vs Load for DIESEL, WCO B10 & SOYA B10

Fig 22. Volumetric Efficiency Vs Load for WCO B20, SOYA B20 & DIESEL

Fig 23. Volumetric Efficiency Vs Load for DIESEL, SOYA B10, SOYA B20, SOYA B25

Fig 24. Volumetric Efficiency Vs Load for DIESEL, WCO B10, WCO B20 & WCO B25

Fig 25.Volumetric Efficiency Vs Load for DIESEL, WCO B10 & WCO B25

Fig 26.Volumetric Efficiency Vs Load for DIESEL, WCO B10, WCO B25 & SOYA B25

CONCLUSIONS

The performance tests were conducted with diesel, and blends of waste cooking oil at different loads and at constant speed (1490 rpm). From the experimental results obtained, waste cooking oil blend B25 are found to be a promising alternative fuel for compression ignition engines.

1. The brake thermal efficiency for all waste cooking oil blends & soybean oil blends was found to be same as compared to diesel at the same load condition.
2. The brake thermal efficiency of waste cooking oil increased by 9.01% compared to diesel at the compression ratio 18 and at load 9 kg for the blend B25. For the blend B10 & B20 the percentage increase in brake thermal efficiency is 1.46%, 1.22% respectively as compared to diesel.
3. The brake specific fuel consumption decreases for all blends of waste cooking oil as compared with diesel. Brake specific fuel consumption of waste cooking oil blend B25 decrease by 13% as compared with diesel.
4. The brake thermal efficiency for all soybean blends was found higher than diesel as well as waste cooking oil at full load condition while working with part load all blends had lower brake thermal efficiency.
5. Brake specific fuel consumption for all soybean blends was found lower at full load as compared to diesel but higher than waste cooking oil.

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